

Carbon Capture and Heating – could we rethink the lime cycle?

Marc Linder, German Aerospace Center (DLR e.V.) and University of Stuttgart, Germany

marc.linder@dlr.de

The technical lime cycle is well known and forms the basis for the production of more than 400 Mio. tons of lime-based products per year¹ – so why should we rethink it?

If we change our perspective from a technical, material-oriented to a circular, energy-oriented viewpoint, we see that an energetic lime cycle would – in principle – allow to store renewable energy without losses, to deliver thermal energy for renewable heating on demand and even capture CO₂ directly from air – all in a closed material cycle and based on worldwide abundant resources. The crucial challenge is to operate it in a manner that allows to utilize its full potential.

An energy-oriented lime cycle

The schemes in Figure 1 compare the known material-oriented lime cycle on the left with the suggested energy-oriented viewpoint on the right.

Figure 1: Left: Technical, material-oriented cycle. Right: Circular, energy-oriented cycle. The main aspects of the respective cycle are highlighted in black; the numbers are explained in the text.

The first, immediately visible, difference is related to the closed appearance of the right cycle whereas the left “cycle” seems open. Since in a material-oriented approach the material is the actual purpose of the whole process chain, its properties are tailored along the way from the source to the final point of use. Naturally, this “cycle” ends where the material fulfills its final purpose. However, a closer look shows that the involved main reactants (H₂O and CO₂) are to a certain extent re-exchanged during this path and therefore – from a material point of view – the cycle is chemically closed: It ultimately tends to the original natural compound lime stone, CaCO₃.^{2,3}

¹ U.S. Geological Survey, Mineral Commodity Summaries, January 2022; [Mineral Commodity Summaries 2022 - Lime \(usgs.gov\)](https://www.usgs.gov/minerals/commodity/lime) (accessed Nov. 18th 2022)

² F. Xi et al. Substantial global carbon uptake by cement carbonation (2016), Nature Geoscience, Vol 9; <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo2840>

³ F. Campo et al. Natural and enhanced carbonation of lime in its different applications: a review (2021) Environmental Technology Reviews, 10:1, 224-237; <https://doi.org/10.1080/21622515.2021.1982023>

The main difference of the energy-oriented cycle (Figure 1, right) is that the lime-based material serves as a mean not as a purpose. Therefore, this cycle can also be physically closed which means that the lime stone is not consumed but can be transported back to restart the cycle. Following this concept, four key processes can be distinguished (compare numbered positions in Figure 1, right):

1. A calcination reactor that uses renewable energy to produce quicklime thereby releasing CO₂ as a point source. The high concentration of CO₂ makes it attractive to capture it for synthetic hydrocarbon production or for ultimate removal from atmosphere in underground or chemical sinks.
2. Storage containers to store the educt CaCO₃ and the solid product CaO at room temperature and ambient pressure. This part decouples the renewable energy supply on the left and the actual demand of energy on the right. Due to the chemical nature of the storage process, the storage duration is in principle without losses.
3. A thermochemical reactor for the exothermal hydration of quicklime – in order to generate heat on demand. The principle is based on the well-known “lime slaking” where liquid water, e.g. from the tap, recombines with quicklime in a highly exothermic reaction.⁴
4. A storage compartment which is open to the atmosphere. Here the carbonization of hydrated quick lime takes place. Thereby CO₂ is captured from the surrounding air. Due to the low concentration of CO₂ in air in combination with the low temperature, this process is slow.⁵

As soon as the re-carbonized material (from process 4) is transported back to the calcination site (process 1), the energy-oriented lime cycle is closed. As a consequence, the upper grey arrow in Figure 1 (right) represents the transport of a chemical energy carrier to a consumer, whereas the lower arrow shows the transport of directly captured CO₂ from the consumer back to the point of calcination.

The bottleneck

Obviously, the fundamental bottleneck of this closed lime cycle is related to the slow reaction rate of the re-carbonation in air, step 4.

However, since a substantial amount of the thermal energy demand follows a clear seasonal trend, an intrinsic challenge for all energy storage options occurs: the storage material is most of the time passively waiting for its use. The proposed idea is therefore to use this so far passive storage period to compensate the slow reaction kinetics of the carbonation reaction. Or in other words: by coupling a long-term storage approach with direct air capture, even the relatively slow carbonation reaction seems sufficiently fast and could therefore be technically used.

Carbon Capture and Heating – CCH

The backbone of this concept is a community-based transport system that transports the different lime-based compounds between the central charging and decentral discharging sites. An analogy, yet not circular, could be the collection of decentral waste to burn it centrally for energy supply. In case of the energy-oriented lime cycle, the community-based transport system is used to deliver centrally stored energy and to collect de-centrally captured CO₂.

⁴ M. Schmidt and M. Linder. A Novel Thermochemical Long Term Storage Concept: Balance of Renewable Electricity and Heat Demand in Buildings (2020), *Frontiers in Energy Research*; <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2020.00137>

⁵ M. Erans et al. Pilot-scale calcination of limestone in steam-rich gas for direct air capture (2019), *Energy Conversion and Management*; X; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecmx.2019.100007>

Figure 2 shows one schematic example of this concept which can be used to estimate first numbers. On the left side, the material is charged by renewable energy and CO₂ is separated (process 1). On the right side, distributed consumers are shown. In each building liquid water is used to discharge the stored thermal energy to generate heat on demand. After this discharging process the reaction product – Ca(OH)₂ – is stored in an open, probably actively ventilated, compartment for direct air capture.

Figure 2: Carbon Capture and Heating – the closed material cycle delivers heat and collects CO₂. The numbers are related to 1 t of captured CO₂, ideally calculated.

The numbers given in Figure 2 are calculated assuming ideal conditions and full conversions. The inner circle shows that 1.3 t of CaO is necessary to deliver around 400 kWh of heat and 2.3 t of CaCO₃ have to be moved in order to transport 1 t of captured CO₂. In order to release the chemically stored thermal energy of 400 kWh, around 400 l of water (e.g. from the tap or collected) have to be added. The required energy to burn the lime stone and drive the whole cycle depends highly on the used technology for the calcination (process 1). The minimal required energy to release 1t of CO₂ from lime stone is around 1,140 kWh. Even though a direct comparison with currently used large industrial-scale calciners is difficult, they require around 1,340 to 3,170 kWh – depending on the used technology.⁶

Obviously, the given numbers scale linearly but in any case the slowest process – the re-carbonation of Ca(OH)₂, process 4 – determines the minimum cycle duration. According to Morales-Flórez et al.⁷ the re-carbonation can reach substantial conversions (even up to 100 %) within 20 to 40 days – depending on the sample's micro structure. Which means that around 10 cycles shown in Figure 2 per year (e.g. 7 in winter 3 in summer) could be a realistic number.

Conclusion

The proposed CCH concept could form the basis for community-oriented energy systems that offer large central storage capacities based on abundant materials, supply chemically stored renewable energy for heating and simultaneously collect captured CO₂ to concentrate it to a point source. If above given estimates can be technically reached, the current CO₂ footprint per capita (in Germany) and around 50 % of the current heat demand per capita could be covered by circulating 10 times per year 2.4 t of lime stone within short distances inside the community.

⁶ I. Szednjy and D. Brandhuber. Stand der Technik zur Kalk-, Gips- und Magnesiaherstellung (2007) Report, Umweltbundesamt, Wien (in German)

⁷ V. Morales-Flórez et al. Hydration and carbonation reactions of calcium oxide by weathering: Kinetics and changes in the micro-structure (2015) Chemical Engineering Journal 265; <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2014.12.062>